

Synergistic Effect Using Organic Base on Extraction of Co(II) Acetyl Acetonate in Xylene

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The adducts formed between Co(II) acetyl acetonate and a number of bases have been identified and their formation constants determined by the synergistic effects of the various organic amines on the extractability of the cobalt into xylene. The results show that the synergism is due to the formation and preferential extraction of 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 adducts.

THE mechanism of synergism in the extraction of Co(II) acetyl acetonate is the formation of base adducts in the organic solvent¹⁻⁷. The formation constant $K_{2,n}$ of the base adduct is a quantitative measure of the synergistic enhancement by the neutral base. Further, it is known that water molecules play an important role in the equilibria of the species in the organic phase⁸⁻¹¹.

where o denotes the organic phase, AcAc : acetyl acetone, n number of ligands L.

Experimental

Reagents and Solutions :

All chemicals were analytical grade reagents, BDH and Merck.

(a) The aqueous phase contains sodium acetate and acetic acid each 0.2M present in the proper ratio to give the required pH while keeping the ionic strength constant at 0.2M. It also contains $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at concentrations ranging from 10^{-2}M to 10^{-3}M .

(b) The organic phase was xylene 0.1M in acetyl acetone (AcAc) and with different molarities of the amines (0.01-0.5M). The amines used were : pyridine (Py) ; 2,2'-dipyridyl (dipy) ; benzylamine (BA), dibenzylamine (DBA), triethylamine (TEA), tri-n-propylamine (TPrA), tri-isooctylamine (TIOA) tribenzylamine (TBA).

Procedure :

Equal volumes of the 2 phases were shaken together till equilibrium, after separation the cobalt was determined complexometrically in the two phases.

Calculation of the formation constant $K_{2,n}$:

The species extracted are neutral complexes. The distribution ratio

$$D = \frac{\text{Total concentration of Co(II) in the organic phase}}{\text{Total concentration of Co(II) in the aqueous phase}}$$

Using the equation given by Akaiwa and Kawanoto, $K_{2,n}$ for the 2 : n adduct $\text{Co}(\text{AcAc})_2$

$$B_n = \frac{[\text{Co}(\text{AcAc})_2 B_n]_o}{[\text{Co}(\text{AcAc})_2]_o [B]_o^n} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

This equation can be transformed to

$$\log \left(\frac{D}{D_0} - 1 \right) = \log \sum_{n=1} K_{2,n} [B]_o^n \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where D_0 is the distribution ratio in the absence of base. Values of D_0 can be obtained from the following equation :

$$K_0 = D_0 \frac{[\text{H}]^n}{[\text{HA}]^n}$$

where K_0 the equilibrium constant, HA the chelating acid (AcAc), n : number of base. To determine $K_{2,n}$ it is sufficient to find D at various pH and at various base concentrations.

Results and Discussion

The dependence on pH of the extraction of $\text{Co}(\text{AcAc})_2$ for different bases is represented in Fig. 1. Increasing the pH, increases the percentage extraction, all bases give enhancement except TIOA, TBA. This may be attributed to the steric effect of these bases.

Fig. 1. Effect of pH and different organic bases on extraction of Co(II) acetylacetonate in xylene.

Effect of base concentration on synergism :

Keeping AcAc at $10^{-1}M$ and Co(II) at $10^{-3}M$, the effect of the solution and the concentration ratio of the added organic base on the distribution ratio of $Co(AcAc)_2$, at room temperature, was investigated and the results are represented graphically in Figs. 2-5 for the different bases.

Fig. 2. Effect of pH and concentration of TPrA on extrn. of $Co(AcAc)_2$ in xylene.

Fig. 3. Effect of pH and concentration of TEA on extraction of $Co(AcAc)_2$ in xylene.

Fig. 4. Effect of pH and concentration of BA on extraction of $Co(AcAc)_2$ in xylene.

Fig. 5. Effect of pH and concentration of pyridine on extrn. of $Co(AcAc)_2$ in xylene.

From these Figs. at fixed pH value (say $pH=7$) where $D_0=0.3891$, the value of $\log D$ and hence $\log \left(\frac{D}{D_0} - 1 \right)$ for each base can be evaluated.

Hence from equation (2), a plot of $\log \left(\frac{D}{D_0} - I \right)$ vs $\log [B]_{\text{total}}$ can be obtained and should yield a straight line, with slope n and intercept $\log K_{2,n}$ which is the formation constant of the reaction

Such a relation is represented in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. $\log \left(\frac{D}{D_0} - I \right)$ vs $\log [B]_{\text{total}}$ for determination of $\log K_{2,n}$ in xylene.

To increase the organic character of the Co(II) acetyl acetonate complex a base is added and this enhances the extraction of the complex in the organic phase. The mechanism by which the

neutral amine adds to the metal chelate in the organic phase depends upon the nature of the complex in the organic phase.

The results indicate that for the pH range 6.5-7.2, the formation constants K of the adducts are almost constant. However, the number of base molecules added is only one for BA and TEA, this may be due to the bulky size of TEA causing large steric hindrance and giving a very weak bond with the $\text{Co}(\text{AcAc})_2$ complex. But Py and TPrA both give di-adducts.

Base	pK_b	$\log K$	n	mean $\log K$
Py	8.82	2.12	2	2.12 ± 0.02
TPrA	3.35	2.22	2	2.22 ± 0.02
BA	4.66	1.97	1	1.87 ± 0.13
TEA	3.22	1.96	1	1.86 ± 0.13

Excess base does not change the identity or stability of the adduct.

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